

16.X-04 PROTEIN CRYSTAL OSCILLATION FILM DATA
PROCESSING: A COMPARATIVE STUDY. J.R. Helliwell,
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A project has been instigated to evaluate the relative performance of different microdensitometers and protein crystal oscillation film data processing packages used in the U.K. The single crystal oscillation data set chosen for study was from a horse spleen apoferritin crystal, space group F432 (cubic with $a = 184.0 \text{ \AA}$, with X-ray data collected on a conventional source at Cu K α wavelength ($1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The particular advantages of this crystal space group system were that only 15° total rotation angle was needed for a complete data set (neglecting a blind region) with four equivalent reflections which could be collected from a single crystal before serious radiation damage of the sample. Hence, by avoiding problems of crystal to crystal scaling, comparisons concentrate on the film scanning and processing methods and with a relatively small computing effort finally arrive at a merged data set with an R sym in each case. Three different types of scanners, the Joyce-Loebl Scandig-3 (used at $50 \mu\text{m}$ and $100 \mu\text{m}$ raster) the Optronics Photoscan ($100 \mu\text{m}$ raster) and a flying spot densitometer are being compared. In total, four Scandigs and three Optronics instruments are being separately used at the various institutions involved in this project. The separate data processing software packages involved utilize both off-line and on-line methods.

Results are presented which compare film scanners (at 50 and 100 micron resolution), orientation matrix calculations, reflection integration and film to film scaling techniques by appropriate reference to quantities such as least squares residuals, R-factors on intensity in each case and an analysis of the agreement of the results of the different methods.

SUMMARY OF PARTICIPANTS' TECHNIQUES

PARTICIPANT	MASTER (μm)	SOFTWARE				COMPUTER TYPE
		POST ALIGN	PROFILE FIT	FILM :FILM :PACK RACING SCALING (24 scale film duty)	PACK :PACK	
A1	50 ^S	X	X 	✓	all.	main frame
A2	100 ^S	X	X A1 A1	✓	all.	main frame
B	100 ^S	✓	X 	X	simult.	mini/main frame
C	100 ^S	X	X A2 A1	X	all.	mini
D	100 ^S	✓	✓	X	all.	mini
E	100 ^S	✓	X A2 A1	X	simult.	mini/main frame
F	100 ^S	X	X 	X	all.	mini.

A to F Random ordering of participants.

KEY

S = TOYCE LOEBL SCANDIG-3

D = OPTRONICS PHOTOSCAN P-1000

X NO

✓ YES

all. = alternate cycles of k, b refinement

simult. = simultaneous refinement of k, b.

INTERNAL SYMMETRY R-FACTORS IN
PACK TO PACK MERGING (QUESTIONNAIRE
DATA)

PARTICIPANT	R _{SYM}	NREF (R _{SYM})	NREF TOTAL	R _{ES} ⁹⁰ LIMIT (Å)
A1	11.3 %	5321	6190	2.698
A1'	14.1 ^N	—	6399	2.698
A2	13.2	5336	6197	2.698
B	21.0 ^N	—	6399	2.73
C	8.0 ^F	—	5164	2.841
D	5.8	—	5756	2.763
E	10.6	3799	4796	2.81
F	6.4 ^F	—	6248	2.81

NOTES

1. 'N' negative I's included.
2. A1' identical to A1 except for inclusion of negatives. For B without -ve's would cross ≈ 18% R_{SYM}.
3. 'F'-R_{sym} calculated on F's.

AGREEMENT ANALYSIS BETWEEN DATA

SETS 'i' and 'j' / NUMBER OF OVERLAPS
BETWEEN 'i' and 'j'.

$R_{ij} \%$ N_{ij}	A1	B	C	D	E	F
A1	0.0	6.0	6.9	5.5	6.0	7.0
B	4748	0.0	6.1	4.4	5.1	6.3
C	4898	4642	0.0	6.2	5.9	7.0
D	5096	4824	4924	0.0	5.1	6.1
E	4653	4327	4416	4571	0.0	6.1
F	5024	4767	4867	5093	4653	0.0

$\langle R_{ij} \rangle$ 6.3 5.6 6.4 5.5 5.6 6.5

$R_{ij} \text{ min}$ 5.5 4.4 5.9 4.4 5.1 6.1
 (with) (D) (D) (E) (B) (B,D) (D,E)

$R_{ij} \text{ max}$ 6.9 6.3 6.9 6.2 6.1 7.0
 (with) (C) (F) (A) (C) (F) (A,C)

$R_{\text{mutual}, i}$ 4.8 4.3 3.7 3.5 4.5 4.8
 (with set b
 best set)

NAEF 5352 4986 5134 5404 4675 6072
 mutual, i

RANKING ORDERS

ORDER	R _{SYM}	$\langle R_{ij} \rangle$	$R_{mutual, i}$	NREF $R_{mutual, i}$
1	D 5.8	D 5.5	D 3.5	F 6.72
2	F 6.4	B 5.6	C 3.7	D 5.404
3	E 10.6	E 5.64	B 4.3	A1 5.353
4	A1 11.3 A2 13.2	A1 6.3	E 4.5	C 5.134
5	B 21.0 (17.0)	C 6.4	A1 4.8 F	B 4.996
6		F 6.5		E 4.675

NOTES

1. R_{SYM} FOR C WAS ON F NOT I AND SO HAS BEEN EXCLUDED

2. NOTE THE WIDER RANGE OF R_{SYM} 4. WITH $\langle R_{ij} \rangle$ AND $R_{mutual, i}$

3. D TOPS NEARLY ALL POSITIONS AND SUBMITTED THE DATA V. QUICKLY.

4. B HAS A LARGE R_{SYM} BUT PERFORMS WELL IN $\langle R_{ij} \rangle$ & $R_{mutual, i}$

5. $\langle R_{ij} \rangle_{scandiz} = 5.7 \pm 0.4$; $\langle R_{ij} \rangle_{opt} = 6.5 \pm 0.1$

6. $\langle R_{mut, i} \rangle_{scandiz} = 4.3 \pm 0.6$; $\langle R_{mut, i} \rangle_{opt} = 4.3 \pm 0.8$

SOFTWARE GENEALOGY

B, C, D, E, F ORIGINATE FROM THE
CAMBRIDGE SOFTWARE
(IDREF, GENERT etc).
MOSCO

A IS OF DIFFERENT ORIGIN

C AND F IDENTICAL SOFTWARE ; DIFFERENT
MODIFICATIONS AT DIFFERENT TIMES.

SOME CONCLUSIONS CONCERNING:-

1. PROFILE FITTING OF D WORTHLESS - WEAK DATA + ALSO AVOIDED PROBLEMS OF CLOSE ROWS, ROW INTERACTIONS.
 2. POST REFINEMENT OF E WORTHLESS (ALSO PROBABLY FOR B AND D).
 3. WEAK TO STRONG FILM SCALING - ONLY USE STRONG REACTIONS ON B FILM UNLIKE A.
 4. DENSITOMETERS - SCANDIG AND OPTONICS PERFORMED AS WELL AS EACH OTHER.
 5. ROTATION CAMERA DATA AND OTHER DATA COLLECTION METHODS. R FACTOR OF FILM AS GOOD AS MUPAC OR DENSITOMETER? NEEDS A COMPARISON $\uparrow$ EARLIER PAPER IN THE JOURNAL.
 6. BENEFITS TO THE PARTICIPANTS ON THE PROJECT - FEEDBACK ON OTHER SYSTEMS; CHANCE TO ADD IMPROVEMENTS AND PROVIDED THE DIGITAL DENSITOMETER DATA IS KEPT TO RECORD THE IMPROVEMENT OVER THE PREVIOUS EFFORT AS A REFERENCE.
FUTURE WORK NEEDED | POSSIBLE
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1. COVARIANCE ANALYSIS TO MORE CLOSELY ISOLATE DIFFERENT ERROR CONTRIBUTIONS
 2. SUBMISSION BY PARTICIPANTS OF A WEAK AND A STRONG FILM DATA FILE.
 3. BROADER RANGE OF PARTICIPANTS.

16.4-01 CENTRAL DATA COLLECTION FACILITY FOR PROTEIN CRYSTALLOGRAPHY, SMALL ANGLE DIFFRACTION AND SCATTERING at the Daresbury Laboratory Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS). By J.R. Helliwell^{1,2}, T.J. Greenhough¹, P. Carr¹, P.R. Moore², A.J. Thompson², G. Hughes², M.M. Przybylski², P.A. Ridley², J.E. Bateman³, J.F. Connolly³ and R. Stephenson³, Keele University¹ and Science Research Council, Daresbury Laboratory² and Rutherford Laboratory³, England.

A centralised data collection facility for synchrotron X-ray diffraction experiments on crystals, fibres and solutions of biological macromolecules is nearing completion at the Daresbury Laboratory Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS). The SRS is based on a 2 GeV electron storage ring with an initial maximum circulatory electron current of 370 mA with a critical wavelength of 3.8Å on the conventional X-ray line and 1.0Å on the wiggler beam line. The X-ray diffraction work-station consists of a vertically focussing platinum coated quartz mirror and a horizontally focussing 10.5° oblique cut Ge(111) triangular perfect monochromator crystal. Intensities at the focus of the optical system are expected to be two orders of magnitude stronger than conventional X-ray sources (rotating anode generators). Carefully controlled tungsten-aluminium slits both before and after the monochromator are available to minimise extraneous X-ray scatter. For protein crystallography an ARNDT-WONACOTT photographic rotation camera is available (see photo) modified for direct, CAMAC based, computer control. Sample cooling facilities over a range -175°C to +10°C are available. Electronic area detection facilities based on a TV image intensifier system are under development for the SRS by Enraf-Nonius Ltd., Delft. For small angle diffraction and scattering experiments a different camera is available allowing up to 5 m between specimen and detector providing exceptionally good spectral resolution (order to order and direct beam). A flat multiwire proportional chamber system is being commissioned with a 20 cm aperture and 1 mm wire pitch capable of handling rates up to 300 kHz with a dedicated histogramming memory to provide a real time acquisition facility for dynamic experiments.

Experimental results on a variety of systems will be presented.